

Research of Long-Term Stability of High Sensitivity Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors for Ultra-Low Differential Pressures

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Abstract — Long-term stability of output characteristics of piezoresistive pressure sensor chips in the form of microelectromechanical system (MEMS) is one of the most important parameters. The research analyzes the variation of useful signal of high sensitive pressure sensor chips and its errors in mechanical and temperature characteristics, which are also time-dependent. The main feature of this study is the application of the previously developed construction of mechanical part, which allows to achieve a balance between extremely high sensitivity and low error rates for ultra-low pressure range. The research demonstrates the changes after 5 years of aging for 24 pressure sensor chip samples (chip dimension 6.15x6.15 mm²) for pressure range of 0.5 kPa with sensitivity $S_{0.5 \text{ after}} = (34.5 \pm 6.0)$ mV/V/kPa, nonlinearity $2K_{NL \ 0.5 \text{ after}} = (0.71 \pm 0.47)$ %/FS and temperature hysteresis up to 0.5% in the temperature range from -30 °C to +60 °C. The results of long-term stability of useful signal shows that the errors for 10 out of 24 samples does not exceed the values of 1.5%, which mostly connects with influence of residual mechanical stresses (RMS) from the assembly design of pressure sensor.

INDEX TERMS— PRESSURE SENSOR, LONG-TERM STABILITY, HIGH SENSITIVITY, NONLINEARITY, TEMPERATURE ERRORS.

I. Introduction

THE market of MEMS pressure sensors continues its rapid development, which is reflected both in the increase of production volume for previously introduced devices and in the opening of new areas for application in various industrial sectors, for example, the devices with wearable functions. The main focus for mass production saves on the application of two most developed pressure conversion methods (piezoresistive and capacitive) in the 5 most demanded market sectors: automotive industry (TPMS, engine and fuel tank, airbags and exhaust gas monitoring), industrial applications (warehouse automation, process and equipment condition monitoring, water and steam pressure analysis in nuclear power plants, robotics for autonomous vehicles, HVAC), consumer electronics (smartphones and wearable electronics, IoT, drones, smart home), aerospace (hydraulics, FADEC, airflow and altitude data) and medical (invasive blood pressure monitoring, respirators and inhalers, ventilators). The volume of MEMS consumption and, in particular, pressure sensors for industry and medicine is small and amounts to about 5% of the sales (number of units) in the world, but since the requirements to the quality of products are many times more stringent relative to the consumer and automotive sectors, the cost of these components is much higher [1,2]. Competition in the market of pressure sensor sales pushes many advanced manufacturing companies not only to produce more than millions or tens of millions of elements per year, but also to develop exclusive high-tech ideas, which are gradually implemented in new series of sensors with improved characteristics.

Developers are constantly striving to validate the relevance of their offerings by analyzing the repeatability of output characteristics over dozens of consecutive batches. This occurs both when the volume of pressure sensor chips is increased by retooling the entire production line for larger wafer diameters or through certain design and manufacturing solutions to reduce chip area, and when innovative solutions are implemented to reduce various types of sensor errors. In addition to analyzing the output characteristics of pressure sensors after assembly operations and artificial processes for operating time checking, which can predict with a certain degree of probability the behavior of devices after operation, the important factor is still the direct study of uncompensated sensor error of long-term stability to guarantee the quality of development. In addition to monitoring the change of useful signal with time, the bias of errors on mechanical and temperature characteristics is a relevant area of research. The long-term stability and temperature hysteresis of output signal are uncompensated errors that largely determine the quality of the sensor itself [3-7]. At the same time, the nonlinearity and temperature coefficient of zero signal and sensitivity can be reduced by signal processing using ASICs [8-10], but the error correlation coefficients can be changed over time too. There is an increased interest of long-term stability of useful signal and errors for low and ultra-low range pressure sensors, as many

different design and process features can cause variations. A unique type of mechanical structure of piezoresistive pressure sensor chip with Wheatstone bridge circuitry for differential pressure measurement of 0.5 kPa is considered. The development of pressure sensor chip for low ranges is one of the most promising tasks, as its solution simultaneously raises the questions on achieving the balance between the sensitivity, overall chip dimensions, low error rates and, in general, the possibilities of mass production. The output characteristics can vary significantly depending on the different applications of low-range pressure sensors. Comparing the output characteristics of such developments [7-17] gives an opportunity to say that the boundary values on sensitivity should be $S > 10$ mV/V/kPa with errors on nonlinearity $2K_{NL} < 1,0$ %/FS, temperature coefficient of zero signal $TCZ < 0,1$ %/°C and temperature hysteresis of zero signal and sensitivity THZ and THS $< 0,5$ %. Despite a number of advantages of capacitive pressure sensors in terms of low power consumption, simplicity of production and small chip size [18-23], it is labor-intensive to achieve an acceptable useful signal in conjunction with precision error. There are two main factors for piezoresistive pressure sensor chips which make effect on useful signal and errors. The first factor is related directly to the chip itself: the influence of certain p-n junction leakage currents on piezoresistors (PRs) regions with different doping levels [24-27], the influence of defectivity [28] and embedded charge in silicon oxide [29], as well as the effect of difference in the temperature coefficient of expansion (TCE) between the metallized layer and silicon on the thinned part of membrane [30-32]. Relaxation of residual mechanical stresses (RMS) in assembly construction of pressure sensor chip [33-37] is the second and more significant factor for low range pressure sensors. Often the design of mechanical chip construction is more rigid and hence stable to certain additional components of RMS effects for a higher range.

Another distinguishing feature of this study is the statistical analysis of output characteristics. In many important reviews of the articles [38-58] about the achievements of various MEMS pressure sensor developments usually present theoretical and experimental data without specifying the number of elements or only for a small sample volume (up to 3 elements), and without information about thermo- and thermocycling before measurements. There are other methods to achieve a balance between useful signal and error for low ranges, which have been presented with batch-by-batch volumetric statistics, for example, the using of new electrical circuit in the form of piezoresistive differential amplifier with negative feedback (PDA-NFL) [43-48,56]. According to the theory of piezjunction effect on BJTs [42,59-62] cases of using deformable and non-deformable BJTs with horizontal structure of p-n-p type conduction and vertical structure of n-p-n type conduction and with a certain set of ratings for all eight PRs for each of the types of BJTs necessary to achieve a balance between high sensitivity, low error on temperature coefficient of output signal and low noise component of output signal are considered. Each design has a set of its own advantages and disadvantages, the ratio of which makes it possible to use some pressure sensor chips for a different sector of industry. It is worth noting that most of the current studies on pressure sensor for low and ultra-low pressure ranges actually lack information on the analysis of temperature characteristics and long-term stability. This research demonstrates how the parameters of 24 high sensitivity pressure sensor samples for differential pressure range of 0.5 kPa changed after 5 years of aging under normal climatic conditions.

II. BASIC TECHNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF HIGH SENSITIVE PRESSURE SENSOR CHIP FABRICATION

Since the main emphasis of this research is directed precisely to the analysis of long-term stability behavior for all output characteristics, so only basic technological features with certain new additions about the design and fabrication of high sensitive pressure sensor chip is presented. All details were described in previous article [14,16]. In articles a detailed justification on the main points of analytical and ANSYS software modeling (Fig. 1a) for the principles of high sensitive pressure sensor chip design (taking into account the technological features of manufacture and creation of a series of topologies for the construction of membrane was demonstrated. The optimal geometry of mechanical structure for the arrangement of PRs in four regions of maximum mechanical stress (MS) creation on the thinned part of membrane between three concentrators in the form of rigid islands (RIs) and the chip frame (Fig. 1b,c) was selected as a result of theoretical and experimental comparative analysis.

The operation of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip is considered without additional amplification of output signal, how it is realized in analogs using an ASIC in a single assembly or into the chip [63-66]. The chip is created on 4-inches wafers with n-type conductivity and crystallographic plane (100). The chip has a contact to the substrate for additional protection of p-n junction (PRs – substrate) when the highest potential equal to the supply voltage U_{sup} is applied. The contact pads of circuit are located on the non-deformable chip frame and is connected to the main body of PRs due to high-alloyed conductor regions of p⁺-type conductivity and metallization layer of aluminum $W_{al} = 0.8$ μm with a distance of at least 80 μm from the wedge of membrane edge. The main body of PRs is located in crystallographic direction $\langle 110 \rangle$ and is formed of a low-alloyed p⁻-type conductivity region with a high piezoresistive coefficient $\pi_{44 p^-} = 1.26 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot Pa^{-1}$ (at room temperature) [67]. The high-alloyed p⁺-type region with low piezoresistive coefficient $\pi_{44 p^+} = 0.32 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot Pa^{-1}$ is also formed along the crystallographic direction $\langle 110 \rangle$ and is required to connect the low-alloyed p⁻-type PR region and metallization on the area of thinned part of membrane. The high-alloyed p⁺-type region is about 12% of resistance of full body of PRs. Low-alloyed p⁻-type regions of different PRs were located in the areas with maximum MS between RIs or RIs and the chip frame. The size of gap between RIs and the length of IRs rib, as well as directly the thickness of thinned part were calculated in such a way to achieve the maximum balance between the creation of high MS values in low-alloyed regions of p⁻-type PRs and a certain deflection of membrane, which directly determines the nonlinearity error. The thinner part of membrane (4.20x4.20 mm²) and, in general, the chip itself (6.15x6.15 mm²)

have square shapes for the top view (Fig. 1c). The mechanical part of chip is created only on the back side using liquid anisotropic etching and finishing with a small addition of isotropic etching to increase the mechanical strength of membrane. The liquid etching of silicon utilizes deposited layer Si_3N_4 (PECVD) and ProTEK polymer coating [70,71] as protection for silicon [68,69]. The geometrical dimensions of mechanical part for pressure range of 0.5 kPa were previously presented in articles [14,16]. It should be noted that the scatter of the thickness of thinned part is rather high for high sensitivity chip, which is naturally the reason for the high scatter in sensitivity and pressure measurement errors. It is reasonable to apply liquid stop etching or deep reactive ion etching (DRIE) for further realizations of high sensitivity pressure sensor chips [72-76].

At the end of process route, the high sensitivity chips on the wafer are selected based on the leakage current between all doped regions p-type conductivity for electrical circuit and the substrate. The leakage current at p-n junctions at room temperature and without the influence of external light does not exceed $I_{\text{rev}} < 10$ nA at reverse bias with voltage $U_{\text{rev}} = 40$ V, which partially guarantees the achievement of low errors of stability on the part of chip operation itself. The mobile charge in SiO_2 layer of Na^+ , Cl^- and other ions was measured, which did not exceed readings of $Q < 5 \cdot 10^{10}$ Cl/cm². Thus, this section shows how the problems with the first factor from the Introduction were solved, i.e., minimizing the stability error of the output signal and errors on the chip.

If technological process mode for joining elements into a micro-assembly structure and further into a sensor case is worked out, then the determining factor for a balance of parameters is the geometrical assembly structure of the high sensitivity chip. It happens because the design should minimize all significant effects on RMS relaxation from any kind of chip connections with the sensor body both in time and at temperature changes (the second factor about long-term stability from the Introduction). The variety of interconnection types and materials used is quite extensive, where each has advantages and disadvantages depending on the applicability. There are many different realization technologies for the micro-assembly of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip and for MEMS in general (before the connection with a metal, ceramic, plastic or housing made of other materials [77,78]): hydrophilic or hydrophobic direct silicon bonding [79], anodic bonding [80], bonding through glass (frit) [81,82], eutectic [83,84], adhesive bonding [85,86], reactive compound [87,88], thermal compression [89,90] or laser-assisted coupling [91]. There are also exclusive micro-assembly technologies, such as in the design of PS³ [92]. The process of silicon-to-silicon bonding via frit is chosen as the method for joining in this study. Further, in addition to the particular type of bonding for the micro-assembly, the type and application method of adhesive for bonding the micro-assembly and the body case have a significant role in RMS reducing (Fig. 2) [3,4,92].

Additionally, in order to increase the value of burst pressure uses stops in the micro-assembly structure when mechanical overloads are applied on both sides of the chip. The presence of assembly elements in the form of stops is taken into account when modeling calculates the membrane bending [14,16], i.e. the membrane bending when applying pressure range of 0.5 kPa should be smaller than the gap between chip and stops. The gaps are formed due to the thickness of frit layers. In this case, the membrane bending does not reach the critical one for destruction of the membrane thinned part and protects due to contact with the stops. The bottom stop is made in the form of an intermediate element between the chip and the pedestal. The bottom stop also has connection area on the chip frame and middle holes for pressure supply from the pedestal. The top stop is made in the form of a regular parallelepiped and connects on both sides of chip, where there are no metal pads. The top stop also has areas without connection with chip for pressure supply from the front side. Pressure is applied to the sensor case through a hole in the lid of pressure sensor case from the front side and through a tube from the back side of the high sensitivity chip. The micro-assembly pedestal of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip to the pressure sensor case is connected using an organosilicon adhesive. After all assembly operations and inspections, including measurement of tightness with helium flow rate not exceeding 10^{-8} m³·Pa/s. The batch of assemblies is subjected to thermocycling (5 cycles from $T = -70$ °C to $T = +130$ °C in 24 hours) and pressure-cycling (7000 cycles of 10X overpressure at temperature $T = +90$ °C and pressure holding time of at least 3 seconds) to remove some RMS.

III. THE LONG-TERM STABILITY OF HIGH SENSITIVE PRESSURE SENSOR CHIP

The mechanical and temperature characteristics for the batch of 62 samples of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip for differential pressure range of 0.5 kPa are presented in the article [14]. This research was done in June 2019. Only 24 samples remain as some of the batch in June 2024, where other samples were used for another research. No additional artificial influences by electrical power, pressure, temperature, or other factors were made during the 5-year period for the batch. Thus, the research presents data on long-term stability of high sensitivity pressure sensor chips after aging in normal climatic conditions without any operation. Due to the increased noise component, the measurement of output signal on all samples was calculated as the arithmetic mean of 5 values obtained for 2.5 seconds. The studies for the batch before and after long-term aging were carried out using identical equipment and under identical conditions including the upward position of chip face (top side). The parameters are analyzed only when the pressure is applied unilaterally from the back side of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip. The parameters of all analyzed output characteristics by batch will be presented as "arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation" from the absolute values of each samples. The sign of parameter changes for each sample will be considered only when analyzing the long-term stability of useful signal.

A. Mechanical characteristics

The following parameters at fixed temperature $T = +25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are considered as mechanical characteristics: zero output signal, sensitivity and nonlinearity error. Table 1 presents in detail the values of mechanical characteristics. Table 1 shows the values on mechanical characteristics without apostrophe is the moment before long-term aging, and with apostrophe is after 5 years of aging. Figures 3 and 4 demonstrate the errors for long-term stability of useful signal after 2 years and 5 years of aging for each of samples. These parameters from Table 1 were calculated using equations (1-6):

$$\Delta U_{0.5} = U_{0.5} - U_{0'} \quad (1)$$

$$S = \Delta U_{0.5} / U_{\text{sup}} / \Delta P_{0.5} \quad (2)$$

$$2K_{\text{NL}} = \frac{\Delta U_{0.25} - \Delta U_{0.5} \cdot (\Delta P_{0.25} / \Delta P_{0.5})}{\Delta U_{0.5}} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta 2K_{\text{NL}} = 2K_{\text{NL}} - 2K'_{\text{NL}} \quad (4)$$

$$dU_{0\text{stab}} = (|U_0| - |U'_0|) \cdot 100\% / \Delta U_{0.5} \quad (5)$$

$$dU_{0.5\text{stab}} = (\Delta U_{0.5} - \Delta U'_{0.5}) \cdot 100\% / \Delta U_{0.5} \quad (6)$$

where U_{sup} - supply voltage equal to 5 V; $\Delta P_{0.5}$ or 0.25 - pressure difference between the back and front side of high sensitivity chip of 0.5 and 0.25 kPa, respectively; U_0 - zero output signal when the pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa, mV; $U_{0.5}$ - output signal when the pressure $\Delta P_{0.5} = 0.5$ kPa, mV; $\Delta U_{0.5}$ or 0.25 - change of output signal under pressure $\Delta P_{0.5} = 0.5$ kPa or $\Delta P_{0.25} = 0.25$ kPa, respectively, mV; S - sensitivity, mV/V/kPa; $2K_{\text{NL}}$ - nonlinearity error under pressure $\Delta P_{0.5} = 0.5$ kPa, %/FS; $dU_{0\text{stab}}$ - stability error of zero output signal, %/FS; $dU_{0.5\text{stab}}$ - stability error of output signal change from pressure $\Delta P_{0.5} = 0.5$ kPa, %/FS.

The limit of zero output signal modulo values is less than 25 mV for the batch of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip for range of 0.5 kPa. The relatively large unbalance of zero output signal connects with large chip area relative to analogs. This drawback can be eliminated by using an ASIC as in the case of high noise component of output signal. The sensitivity is $S = (33.8 \pm 6.2)$ mV/V/kPa instead of the previously reported values of $S = (34.2 \pm 6.9)$ mV/V/kPa, since part of the batch from previous studies was used in another research. Analyzing of changing in modulus of zero output signal of each samples shows a multidirectional shift in the balance with time, where 20 of 24 samples have the error of $dU_{0\text{stab}} < 1.5\%$ /FS after 5 years of aging (Fig. 2a). The average modulus error into the batch for long-term stability of zero signal over 5 years is $dU_{0\text{stab}} = (0.79 \pm 0.70)$ %/FS. 22 of 24 samples in the case of sensitivity long-term stability showed a unidirectional increase in sensitivity over 5 years with a mean modulus error into the batch of $dU_{0.5\text{stab}} = (2.67 \pm 2.02)$ %/FS. Additionally, 4 of 24 samples showing a slight decrease in sensitivity over the first 2 years of aging and increase after 5 years of aging. A similar pattern is observed for long-term stability of zero output signal, where 3 of 24 samples changed sign. The change in sensitivity is more powerful relative to zero output signal, so only 11 of 24 samples have acceptable error rates relative to their analogs of $dU_{0\text{stab}} < 1.5\%$ /FS after 5 years of aging (Fig. 2b). Table 1 also shows that most samples have a reduction of nonlinearity error (not modulo) $\Delta 2K_{\text{NL}} = 0.04$ %/FS or on the order of 5% of the initial error value.

B. Temperature characteristics

Research of temperature characteristics for the batch of high sensitivity pressure sensor chips is tested for two temperature ranges: from $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and from $+20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The rate of temperature change in a thermal chamber is $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The endurance of temperature boundary values is 1 hour. The studies are carried out in 64 dm^3 volume chamber, which has its own error as a temperature gradient in the chamber volume and temperature hysteresis after temperature change to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ inside it. Additional precision temperature control is performed using a group of small-sized temperature sensors based on a Schottky diode with a planar arrangement of electrodes (PSD chip), previously developed specifically for pressure sensors and presented in article [93]. The temperature gradient across the thermal chamber is about $0.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The same temperature unbalance within the volume can be neglected, if all samples remained stationary during the test period. The temperature hysteresis of the thermal chamber is about $0.08\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is insignificant, because it is equivalent to the average error for high sensitivity pressure sensor chip of about 0.004%. Temperature hysteresis and coefficient for zero output signal and sensitivity are considered as parameters for temperature characteristics using the following equations:

$$\text{THZ} = \frac{U_0(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}}) - \Delta U'_0(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})}{|\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\% \quad (7)$$

$$\text{THS} = \frac{\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}}) - \Delta U'_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})}{|\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\% \quad (8)$$

$$\text{TCZ} = \frac{U_0(T_{-30^{\circ}\text{C}/+60^{\circ}\text{C}}) - U_0(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})}{|\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})| \cdot (T_{-30^{\circ}\text{C}/+60^{\circ}\text{C}} - T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})} \cdot 100\% \quad (9)$$

$$\text{TCS} = \frac{\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{-30^{\circ}\text{C}/+60^{\circ}\text{C}}) - \Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})}{(T_{-30^{\circ}\text{C}/+60^{\circ}\text{C}} - T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})/10 |\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\% \quad (10)$$

where THZ and THS – temperature hysteresis of zero output signal and sensitivity, respectively, %; TCZ and TCS – temperature coefficient of zero output signal and sensitivity, respectively, %/°C; $U_0(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})$ - zero output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C before the temperature change in the chamber, mV; $U_0(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})$ - zero output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C after the temperature change in the chamber, mV; $\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})$ - change of output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0.5$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C before the temperature change in the chamber, mV; $\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{+20^{\circ}\text{C}})$ - change of the output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0.5$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C after the temperature change in the chamber, mV; $U_0(T_{-30^{\circ}\text{C}/+60^{\circ}\text{C}})$ - zero output signal when pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa and temperature $T = -30$ °C or $T = +60$ °C, mV; $\Delta U_{0.5}(T_{-30^{\circ}\text{C}/+60^{\circ}\text{C}})$ - change of output signal when pressure $\Delta P = 0.5$ kPa and temperature $T = -30$ °C or $T = +60$ °C, mV. The error indices for all temperature characteristics specified here and in article [14] are not significantly different, but are actually in the same range relative to the arithmetic mean values with a scatter as a function of standard deviation. Figure 4 shows all 4 parameters of temperature characteristics for the batch of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip for two temperature ranges and for two time points before and after long-term aging. The errors of temperature characteristics have a wide enough range of values between the samples in the batch, but if we evaluate the change of parameters by its "arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation" from the module of absolute values of each sample, so it can be noted that relative to the initial values after 5 years of aging:

- The average THZ values increased slightly by 0.015%, but the range of values for the batch more significantly decreased by 0.060%;
- The average THS decreased, but also not significantly, by 0.017%, while, as with THZ, the range of values for batch decreased more by 0.058%;
- The greatest changes showed for TCZ at two temperature ranges (especially from +20 °C to +60 °C). The average TCZ values relative to the initial readings decreased significantly by 0.006%/°C, as it happened for the range of values for batch by 0.016%/°C;
- TCS also decreased, but less significantly. The average values of TCS decreased by 0.005%/°C, the range of values for batch decreased by 0.025%/°C.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The effectiveness of the proposed development as high sensitivity pressure sensor chips for ultra-low pressure range of 0.5 kPa was demonstrated on the basis of presented results of long-term stability for useful output signal and errors. The relevance of this development was analyzed according to the set of previously presented solutions, consisting of both design features of mechanical part construction for high sensitivity pressure sensor chip on piezoresistive effect with Wheatstone bridge circuitry, and technological features of the selected route for chip realization (the level of impurity doping for different chip areas, analysis of ionic current in silicon oxide, location and type of metal tracks and pads on the chip frame, etc.) and features of assembly. The changes in all mechanical and temperature characteristics were analyzed to confirm the effectiveness of the development application on the batch of 24 samples. There were analyzed the changes of useful output signal and errors, which were obtained actually immediately after production with thermocycling and pressure-cycling, as well as after long-term aging during 5 years in normal climatic conditions. Individual parameters such as zero output signal, sensitivity, long-term stability of zero signal and sensitivity, and nonlinearity were considered for each sample separately. The main conclusions on the change of mechanical and temperature characteristics specifically for high sensitivity pressure sensor chips after long-term aging are as follows:

- Changing of long-term stability errors from the absolute values of zero output signal is multidirectional. In most cases (20 of 24 samples) the error does not exceed the values of $dU_{0 \text{ stab}} = 1.5$ %/FS for 5 years.
- The sensitivity (22 of 24 samples) increases unidirectionally, which probably indicates the influence of RMS relaxation in the assembly design of pressure sensor, especially considering the use of the top to protect the chip on mechanical overload. The change in sensitivity for the batch of high sensitivity pressure sensor chips after 5 years of aging is $dU_{0.5 \text{ stab}} = (2.7 \pm 2.0)$ %/FS, which is significantly higher than the zero signal stability;
- Also, the influence of RMS from the assembly design is evidenced by the unidirectional strict reduction in nonlinearity from $2K_{\text{NL before}} = (0.75 \pm 0.56)$ %/FS to $2K_{\text{NL after}} = (0.71 \pm 0.46)$ %/FS. The tendency of the assembly structure to balance unstressed state of membrane is observed regardless of whether the structure was initially curved upward or concave downward on RMS effects and influence of inertial mass of RIs, which pull the membrane deflection downward when the chip is arranged face up.
- The temperature characteristics also clearly demonstrate the cause of the presence of RMS, since in most cases the total picture of the average value and its range is reduced. For clarity, let us analyze not each of the parameter values with certain conventional units, but its indicators in the form of percentage of relative change for each error after 5 years:
 - Average value of TCZ decreased by 12% and its range decreased by 19%;
 - Average value of TCS decreased by 2% and its range decreased by 31%;

- Average value of THS decreased by 7% and its range decreased by 21%;
- Average value of THZ increased by 6% and its range increased by 16%;

There is the increase only in the average value of THZ with the reduction in its range of values (as in the case of the ranges for all other parameters), which remains within fairly low error rates of up to 0.5%. The THS does not exceed the values of 0.4%, TCZ is less than 0.09%/°C and TCS is less than 0.30%/°C. As mentioned earlier in the Introduction, different developments have its own balance between advantages and disadvantages. In the case of application of the proposed design and technological solutions for the classical electric circuit of Wheatstone bridge, the advantages of the development consist in maintaining high sensitivity $S = (34.2 \pm 6.9) \text{ mV/V/V/kPa}$ while achieving low nonlinearity error $2K_{NL} = (0.71 \pm 0.47) \%/\text{FS}$ and long-term stability of useful output signal up to 1.5% over 5 years, which are confirmed by statistical data in 10 of 24 samples. It is worth noting that the author cannot previously found similar data among published studies on the long-term stability of the useful output signal, as well as mechanical and temperature characteristics for high sensitivity pressure sensor chips. The solution for the initial reduction of errors due to the influence of RMS in temperature characteristics and long-term stability immediately after the fabrication of sensors (with work-up by thermocycling and pressure-cycling) can serve as a further modernization of geometry for mechanical decoupling and methods of its connection from the case to chip. As a result of the presented research: the relevance of using the developed high sensitivity pressure sensor chip for ultra-low ranges of 0.5 kPa was proved, as the extremely high sensitivity values with optimally low value of errors for mechanical and temperature characteristics saved during 5 years of aging.

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Fig. 1. High sensitivity pressure sensor chip: (a) MS distribution in the region between RIs and the chip frame; (b) Photo of the front side of chip; (c) Photo of the membrane structure from the back side of chip.

Fig. 2. Assembly design for high sensitivity pressure sensor chip: (a) schematic representation of pressure sensor assembly; (b) photo of micro-assembly design; (c) enlarged schematic representation of micro-assembly design.

Fig. 3. Graph for dependence of long-term stability errors for high sensitivity pressure sensor chip during 5 years: (a) zero output signal; (b) sensitivity.

Fig. 4. Temperature characteristics of high sensitivity pressure sensor chip before and after aging during 5 years: (a) THZ and THS; (b) TCZ; (c) TCS

TABLE I
VALUES OF MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND LONG-TERM STABILITY ERRORS OF ZERO OUTPUT SIGNAL AND SENSITIVITY DURING 5 YEARS FOR HIGH SENSITIVITY PRESSURE SENSOR CHIP OF ULTRA-LOW RANGE OF 0.5 kPa.

Samples/ Parameters	Before aging				After aging				Long-term stability		
	No	U ₀ , mV	ΔU _{0.5} , mV	S, mV/V/kPa a	2K _{NL} , %/FS	U ₀ , mV	ΔU _{0.5} , mV	S, mV/V/kPa a	2K _{NL} , %/FS	Δ2K _{NL} , %/FS	dU _{0 stab} , %/FS
1	3.8	102.8	41.1	0.65	4.3	103.3	41.3	0.65	0.01	-0.25	0.49
2	1.0	92.0	36.8	1.52	1.5	92.1	36.8	1.55	-0.03	-0.23	0.15
4	16.3	86.2	34.5	0.25	12.7	87.6	35.0	0.25	0.00	2.11	1.50
5	-4.9	96.2	38.5	0.88	-4.6	96.6	38.6	0.89	-0.01	0.19	0.38
6	21.5	103.1	41.3	0.29	23.7	106.1	42.4	0.28	0.01	-1.04	2.83
9	6.0	89.2	35.7	1.83	6.5	86.8	34.7	1.65	0.17	-0.17	0.41
10	12.2	115.0	46.0	1.28	12.6	115.4	46.2	1.31	-0.03	-0.39	4.47
20	-2.7	74.5	29.8	0.17	-3.3	77.8	31.1	0.18	-0.01	0.65	6.80
21	-3.5	69.7	27.9	0.84	-2.6	74.4	29.8	0.79	0.05	1.34	4.51
23	2.9	67.3	26.9	0.21	1.1	70.3	28.1	0.22	-0.01	2.27	4.55
25	-10.8	63.4	25.4	0.15	-7.9	66.3	26.5	0.16	-0.01	0.01	5.65
31	0.4	82.3	32.9	0.39	0.4	87.0	34.8	0.38	0.01	-0.69	3.22
32	5.0	91.2	36.5	0.38	5.6	91.8	36.7	0.34	0.03	1.30	4.85
34	-7.6	88.6	35.4	0.36	-7.7	89.1	35.6	0.32	0.04	1.17	4.38
36	13.6	75.8	30.3	0.29	12.8	72.6	29.0	0.40	-0.10	-1.43	0.99
37	4.4	79.4	31.8	1.03	3.0	82.2	32.9	1.04	-0.01	1.50	1.07
38	5.8	63.8	25.5	0.42	6.7	65.8	26.3	0.41	0.02	-0.01	0.53
40	3.0	54.1	21.6	0.64	1.6	56.7	22.7	0.59	0.05	-0.01	1.17
41	-9.0	63.9	25.6	0.10	-7.5	66.7	26.7	0.21	-0.11	-0.37	0.61
42	-0.2	100.4	40.2	1.26	3.3	104.7	41.9	1.18	0.09	-0.07	0.59
45	-13.7	97.9	39.1	1.51	-17.1	98.8	39.5	1.44	0.07	0.89	3.56
47	-15.7	93.6	37.4	1.12	-12.5	94.6	37.8	1.03	0.09	-1.49	4.30
49	7.8	85.9	34.3	0.99	-7.9	86.3	34.5	0.79	0.19	-0.28	-2.61
50	0.9	93.9	37.6	1.05	0.9	95.0	38.0	1.05	0.00	0.48	-3.99
Module average	-	84.6	33.8	0.75	-	86.2	34.5	0.71	-	0.79	2.67
Modulus spread	-	15.4	6.2	0.56	-	14.9	6.0	0.47	-	0.70	2.02